

SAMPLE

Group	Age	Gender	Working entity type	Position	Years of experience	Area of knowledge
Biotechnology researchers	between 41 and 50	Male	University	Associate professor	16 to 20	Chemical engineering
Biotechnology researchers	between 51 and 60	Male	Research Center	Associate Scientist	Over 25	Chemical engineering
Biotechnology researchers	between 51 and 60	Male	Research Center	Associate Scientist	Over 25	Microbiology
Biotechnology researchers	between 22 and 30	Male	University	Assistant professor	Under 5	Physical Chemistry
Biotechnology researchers	between 41 and 50	Male	University	Associate professor	16 to 20	Chemical engineering
Biotechnology researchers	Over 60	Female	Research Center	Associate scientist	Over 25	Environmental technologies
Biotechnology researchers	between 41 and 50	Female	Research Center	Senior Technician in Laboratory Activities	11 to 15	Chemical engineering
Biotechnology researchers	between 41 and 50	Female	University	Associate professor	21 to 25	Chemical engineering
Biotechnology researchers	between 41 and 50	Female	University	Associate professor	16 to 20	Chemical engineering
Biotechnology researchers	between 31 and 40	Female	University	Associate professor	16 to 20	Chemical engineering
Biotechnology researchers	between 41 and 50	Female	University	Associate professor	16 to 20	Chemical engineering
Biotechnology researchers	between 41 and 50	Male	University	Assistant professor	21 to 25	Chemical engineering
Communication experts	between 41 and 50	Male	Advertising agency	Chief Creative Officer	21 to 25	Audiovisual communication and advertising
Communication experts	between 31 and 40	Male	ONG	Advocacy and Campaigns Technician	6 to 10	Sociology

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Communication experts	between 41 and 50	Male	Advertising agency	Production manager	16 to 20	Applied economy
Communication experts	between 31 and 40	Male	Advertising agency	Creative director	11 to 15	Business organization
Communication experts	between 41 and 50	Male	Advertising agency	Founder	Over 25	Audiovisual communication and advertising
Communication experts	between 31 and 40	Male	Advertising agency	Creative director	6 to 10	Journalism
Communication experts	between 41 and 50	Male	Advertising agency	Chief Growth Officer	16 to 20	Audiovisual communication and advertising
Communication experts	between 41 and 50	Male	Freelance	Creative director	16 to 20	Audiovisual communication and advertising
Communication experts	between 31 and 40	Male	Advertising agency	Senior Creative	6 to 10	Audiovisual communication and advertising
Communication experts	between 41 and 50	Male	Advertising agency	Founder	Over 25	Audiovisual communication and advertising

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